

Politics I

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ABSTRACT

Politics I is a new work of participatory and web-based computer music that explores concerns about the audience as a political public. Aiming to reveal the politics within musical creation, *Politics I* integrates composition with natural language processing techniques and digitally synthesizes music based on the content of textual inputs from the audience. The textual inputs are submitted via text message or tweet using Twilio’s enterprise messaging service API and Twitter’s API. Through SuperCollider, Ableton Live, Processing, and Python, the resulting musical work makes audible the process by which aesthetic power is shared within participatory musical spaces. The work draws upon the commonly deployed Model-View-Controller software design pattern in a flask-based web application to sonify submitted texts as “views” and simultaneously responds to users with text messages and tweets describing how their texts impacted to sound of the work. At the same time, the messages are rendered to a screen through a Processing sketch that is projected to the front of the house. The work has three movements: Digital Discourse, Cybernetic Republic, and Technoautocracy, which each mediate the audience’s politics of aesthetic preference in unique ways.

1. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

In *Politics I*, the computer music takes in texts submitted by the audience and converts them into sound. Applications recently developed to that allow for audience participation and influence in the synthesis of sound include Dahl, Herrera, and Wilkerson’s *TweetDreams*, and Jason Freeman’s *Glimmer* [4, 8]. There has also been extensive prior research into the sonification of text-based datasets through semantic computing. Hermann, Nehls, Eitel, Barri, and Gammel’s *#tweetscapes* sonifies multiple kinds of data from incoming German-language tweets, such as distance from Germany’s “center”, whether the tweet is a reply, or the retweet count [9]. Seiça, Lopes, Martins, and Cardodo’s study and implementation of “Sonifying Twitter’s Emotions Through Music” utilizes the Stanford CoreNLP toolkit to analyze the emotional qualities of tweets and maps them onto modal and harmonic progressions linked to emotional state that are drawn from psychological research [6]. Prior work on participatory music from a computationally expressive perspective can also be seen in the work of Sang Won Lee, Anna Xambó, Gerard Roma, Visda Gourdarzi, and Abram Hindle [1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 10].

Some of the above-mentioned participatory applications (e.g.

TweetDreams and *Glimmer*) are presented as musical works; yet, they have not explored how, during a performance, the ceding of some musical choices to a concert-going public generates a self-driven politics of aesthetic preference. Similarly, the research into sentiment and text sonification (e.g. *#tweetscapes* and Seiça et al.) either does not provide for real-time interaction with the software and therefore limits (or outright excludes the possibility of) a participatory musical experience or does not take steps towards revealing meta-political structures within and without the software. Many of the cited examples from the literature are expressly interested in the social dimension and HClIs (e.g. *Crowd in C*, *Glimmer*, and *Reactable*) and not necessarily in the political dimensions.

2. ABOUT

2.1 System Description

In order to display the audience’s internal political structures via the interactive system, the system utilizes a platforms and protocols in wide enough use so that the audience is not prevented from participation by lack of access. Therefore, *Politics I* is set up to be able to access the platform application programming interfaces (APIs) of Twitter, as well as take in text messages through a third-party message servicer like Twilio. For platforms that provide access to their API, the system scrapes for a pre-set and pre-announced hashtag keyword so as to localize textual submissions to the concert hall or livestreamed audience. *Politics I* is also designed such that audience ‘onboarding’ is quick and intuitive, and so that sonic results are aesthetically gripping through an extensive testing and revision process that has occurred over the course of spring 2022. This interactive system is structured in such a way that the accretion of incoming texts meaningfully impacts the sonified output and is recognizable to the audience in real time.

Further, the system derives computational linguistic data through the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK), such as sentiment analysis, part of speech tagging, and text comparison for deployment to the sonification and synthesis portion of the program. To assess and compare the content of the texts, *Politics I* has the capability to analyze similarity through cosine similarity, WordNet ranking, and Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency algorithms, however, the current iteration utilizes Levenshtein distance—a general metric for string comparison.

Finally, the system passes data garnered from these natural language processing techniques through Open Sound Control to SuperCollider and/or through to Ableton Live (depending on the version running) and visuals are rendered in Processing. With these conditions set, the system is able to sonify the data extracted from the input texts, and depending on the movement of the work, the aggregate discourse of the room.

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3. MOVEMENT OUTLINES

Each movement represents a different mode of political interaction, and has different modes of translating audience submitted texts into sound synthesis

3.1 Digital Discourse

This movement continuously generates short clips of music based on the contents of each individually submitted text. It relates submitted texts to one another via text-comparison algorithms and bases the similarity of the sound synthesized on the closeness of the similarity scores. The system also senses changes in the 'average' topic discussed. After a 30-second time window, the work generates an average 'topic' value for the just concluded window and compares it to the average 'topic' value of the prior window. The difference between these two values, then, determines the number of chords and the rate by which the harmonic content of the work changes in the upcoming window.

3.2 Cybernetic Republic

In this movement, the audience votes on a select number of musical options that are then synthesized live in a series of rounds. Each 'round' has a voting period and a resting period. During the resting period, the options for the next round are displayed to the audience, and the audience is given a chance to listen to the result of the previous round's selections. When a voting period ends, the highest vote-getter is selected for audio generation.

3.3 Technoautocracy

In this movement, the audience is given very little control over sonic results. If the audience expresses negative sentiment toward the sounds being produced through their submitted texts, the system will respond aggressively with increasingly louder sounds. If a large majority of the audience members express sustained, negative sentiment toward the sounds produced, the 'autocracy' will collapse into an outro. Conversely, if enough audience members continue to express positive sentiments towards the music, or they are unable to organize to meet the threshold to advance the musical form, the 'autocracy' will be sustained.

4. WORK SAMPLES

- Technoautocracy: <https://youtu.be/3uytDpRv-Qo>
- Digital Discourse: <https://youtu.be/baamZgP8fdk>
- Cybernetic Republic: <https://youtu.be/hpi6xew1laA>

5. TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS

Stereo output + Subs; Stable internet connection; Projector and/or stream key; HDMI cable; HDMI Splitter for streaming and projecting in person

6. BIOGRAPHY

Composer Eric Lemmon's artistic practice and academic research is preoccupied with the politics that circumscribe and are woven into our musical technologies and institutions. His music has been reviewed by the *New York Times* and featured on WQXR's Q2 and has been performed in venues ranging from underground bars (le) Poisson Rouge and SubCulture to the DiMenna Center for Classical Music and FIGMENT arts festival on Governor's Island. Eric's work has been recognized locally and internationally with grants and residencies like MetLife's Creative Connections Grant, UMEZ and LMCC Arts Engagement Grants, multiple Puffin

Foundation Grants, a Tofte Lake Center Emerging Artist Residency, a Can Serrat International Artist Residency, a Westben Performer-Composer Residency, and ConEd's Exploring the Metropolis Residency. Further, he has been awarded a Mancini Fellowship, a long-term fellowship from the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD), Stony Brook University's Presidential Dissertation Completion Fellowship, and a Fulbright Award for his artistic research and profile as a performer. Eric has written works for Yarn|Wire, Cadillac Moon Ensemble, Jacqueline LeClaire, and The Chelsea Symphony. He is a member of the experimental and technology-focused music collective Ensemble Decipher and is currently a Ph.D. candidate in Music Composition at Stony Brook University.

7. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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